

SECURE INFORMATION TRANSMISSION BY EMBEDDING COMPRESSED TEXT DATA IN AN IMAGE

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ABSTRACT

The transmission of patient medical information over the internet poses significant challenges due to the risk of unauthorized access by hackers who may illicitly get the data. This work proposes embedding compressed text data using DWT for safe information transport. The brain image of a patient is analyzed, and the patient details are integrated into the brain image utilizing the Least Significant Bit (LSB) approach. The patient's textual information is immediately incorporated into the brain imaging utilizing the Least Significant Bit (LSB) approach. The Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) is utilized to compress the patient's textual information, subsequently embedding it into the patient's brain image to produce a stego image of the brain. The performance characteristics of the embedding procedure utilizing DWT and those that do not utilize DWT are compared. The results obtained with DWT are much superior.

Keywords: DWT, LSB, Embedding, Extracting, Steganography

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1. INTRODUCTION

Secure communication has become essential in the digital age, especially in light of growing worries about data security and privacy. Steganography, which entails hiding secret data within a cover medium like pictures, audio, or video, is one of the methods created to guarantee safe information transmission. Steganography conceals the existence of secret information, making it nearly imperceptible to unauthorized users, in contrast to cryptography, which jumbles the data's content. Due to the extensive use of images and the capacity to embed substantial volumes of data without appreciably compromising image quality, image-based steganography is one of the most often used steganographic techniques.

LSB encoding is one of the most popular techniques in image steganography. This method embeds hidden information by altering the least important portions of an image's pixel values. The simplicity and effectiveness of LSB-based steganography enable large data capacities with little processing overhead. Despite these advantages, LSB-based methods are frequently criticized for being susceptible to attacks such as cropping, noise addition, and compression, which can result in the loss of concealed data or a deterioration in image quality.

Numerous strategies have been introduced in image-based steganography to attain imperceptibility and substantial capacity for data embedding. Prominent techniques include LSB steganography and DWT-based steganography. Both strategies have been thoroughly investigated for their effectiveness in concealing confidential information within digital photographs. Researchers have looked into combining LSB with more sophisticated methods like the DWT in order to overcome the limitations of LSB. A mathematical process known as DWT breaks down an image into its low and high-frequency components. DWT-based methods seek to improve the security and resilience of steganography systems by embedding secret data into the wavelet coefficients as opposed to directly into the image pixels. Data that is embedded in the frequency domain has the advantage of being less vulnerable to distortions brought about by common image processing techniques like scaling or compression.

This study examines the performance of LSB-based image steganography, both with and without DWT integration. It aims to compare the two methods' resilience, security, data embedding capability, and imperceptibility. The Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) is used to evaluate the stego-image's imperceptibility. The embedding capacity quantifies the amount of data that can be concealed inside the image without causing noticeable deterioration, and the technique's resilience to attacks such as cropping and compression is assessed. This study aims to determine whether adding DWT enhances the security, effectiveness, and resilience of LSB-based steganography by contrasting the enhanced DWT-based LSB approach with the conventional LSB method. The results may have important ramifications for creating safer and more effective steganographic methods for digital watermarking, data protection, and secure communication.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

This section thoroughly reviews steganography and research on data embedding for secure communication. This literature analysis examines both approaches' concepts, advantages, disadvantages, and advancements and investigates how the amalgamation of LSB and DWT may provide superior performance for secure communication.

Shukla et al. [1] proposed a methodology that can utilize any image in JPG (JPEG) or PNG format, along with the text as input, to produce the text embedded within the image as output. This paper discusses retrieving the original text on the receiver's side without any data loss. Two classical encryption techniques, specifically Substitution and Transposition ciphers, are employed to enhance the security of transmitted text. Albkosh et al., [2] presented augmented data transmission by improving the LSB steganography technique.

The data will be placed in arbitrary bit locations of pixels to enhance security between the source and destination. RGB photos from the Mendeley benchmark database were utilized as cover images for testing, incorporating varying amounts of text data. The findings in this research demonstrate that the improved technology has augmented data transmission capacity with increased security. Rafrastara et al., [3] presented an altered inverted LSB method. The prior study employed the inverted LSB approach utilizing a two-bit LSB pattern on the second and third bits. The calculation of bit alterations in each pattern will ascertain the execution of the inverted LSB operation. This research advocates for utilizing the LSB three-bit pattern derived from the second, third, and fourth bits of the LSB. The objective is to reduce LSB alterations in every cover image pixel. Tests demonstrate that the inverted LSB approach employing three LSB patterns yields superior results compared to the two-bit LSB pattern.

Ramapriya and Kalpana [4] The proposed technique operates in the spatial domain. This paper enhances the embedding capacity of a concealed image file while maintaining minimal noise interference. This work focuses on a novel method for embedding hidden data within images utilizing the LSB technique in conjunction with Hamming code. This approach exhibits low apparent distortion in image quality. The Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) data were analyzed to demonstrate the efficacy of the suggested technique in embedding within the cover image. Banerjee et al., [5] The research study presents an innovative enhancement of LSB steganography. It employs LSB steganography to substitute the Least Significant Bits of the carrier picture with the binary representation of the encoded text, following the application of various mathematical functions such as polynomials, integrals, and differentials. These functions are invoked arbitrarily to encode text. Consequently, facilitating randomness in text encoding provides a secure and efficient method for encryption and decryption. Hu [6] presented a model utilizing the optimized LSB technique to embed target information implicitly within the image. The model initially encodes the text and refines the LSB technique using a random search algorithm to generate an image after embedding the information. The output image is evaluated using SSIM (Structural Similarity Index Measure), MSE (Mean Squared Error), and PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio) and is compared to the original unimproved LSB algorithm, demonstrating that the optimized LSB technique exhibits enhancements over the original version. Ghazanfari et al., [7] introduced an innovative technique for picture steganography, termed LSB ++, which enhances LSB + image steganography by minimizing alterations to the perceptual and statistical characteristics of the cover image. We identify specific sensitive pixels that influence signal properties and subsequently secure them from the additional bit embedding process of the LSB+ approach by implementing a novel embedding key. The evaluation results indicate that our technique can mitigate possibly detectable alterations resulting from the embedding process without diminishing the embedding capacity.

Thangadurai and Sudha Devi [8] Provide a comprehensive understanding of LSB-based picture steganography and its applications across multiple file formats. This research also examines the existing image-based steganography techniques in conjunction with cryptographic methods to attain security. Priyadharshini et al., [9] The emphasis is on safeguarding the confidentiality and integrity of medical pictures. Integrity and confidentiality may generally be attained using encryption, a form of cryptography. Steganography is utilized to add an additional degree of security to medical imaging. This paper employs a one-time pad encryption scheme to encrypt a medical image, which is subsequently embedded within a cover image to produce a stego image, enhancing the system's resilience against attackers.

This work implements the aforementioned method using MATLAB, and the experimental results are compared with the concealment of the medical image with LSB steganography without encryption (one layer of protection). Multiple formats of medical images have been considered, including DICOM, TIFF, BMP, and JPEG. The results indicate that integrating encryption with steganography yields superior performance compared to the exclusive use of steganography in terms of MSE and PSNR metrics. Pooranakala and Vanita Jaitly [10] The suggested method seeks to improve the security of medical images while transmitting over public networks. The procedure has three primary stages: compression, encryption, and embedding. This research employs a multi-step method to protect the integrity and confidentiality of medical pictures. The medical image is initially compressed utilizing the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) method to diminish its size and eradicate noise. Subsequently, the compressed image is encrypted utilizing the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) technique to guarantee confidentiality. The encrypted image is safely embedded under a cover image via the Least Significant Bit (LSB) steganographic technique to produce a stego image.

Wallace et al., [11] developed to apply the least significant bit (LSB) steganography technique for both grayscale and colored images. The algorithm was evaluated using publicly accessible medical picture datasets and publicly accessible medical test findings. An evaluation metric assessed the disparity between the original image and those embedded with encoded messages. The exercise results indicate positive relationships between the input message size and the MSE and PSNR. It also indicates that as the quantity of images increases, the time required to encode the messages per image remains effectively constant. The program has demonstrated efficacy in concealing medical data within medical photographs.

3. PROPOSED MODEL

3.1. PROPOSED MODEL WITH LSB TECHNIQUE WITHOUT DWT

The suggested steganography model utilizes the LSB methodology, a prevalent way of concealing hidden data within digital images. This model operates exclusively in the spatial domain, directly altering the image's pixel values without employing complex transformations such as DWT. As the LSB denotes the smallest value in pixel data, modifying these bits results in negligible visible deformation to the image, rendering the concealed information challenging to discern. This approach offers simplicity, efficiency, and a considerable capacity for data embedding, enabling substantial amounts of information to be disguised inside the image. Nevertheless, LSB steganography possesses intrinsic limitations, chiefly its susceptibility to image processing assaults. Picture compression (notably JPEG), noise introduction, and cropping can readily compromise or entirely obliterate the concealed data. Moreover, LSB-based techniques sometimes exhibit deficiencies in resilience and security, as the data is directly incorporated inside the pixel values, rendering it vulnerable to identification by statistical analysis. The model emphasizes the encoding and decoding of text-based confidential information into a picture by utilizing the least significant bit of the image's pixel values. This method provides simplicity and is suitable in scenarios where strong security and robustness are not paramount considerations.

3.1.1 EMBEDDING MODEL

The procedure commences with the input image. The initial duty is to verify the image's dimensions to confirm sufficient capacity for the concealed data. The total number of pixels in the image and the bits used to encode the secret data dictate this. Each pixel in a picture has three color channels: Red, Green, and Blue (RGB), with each channel represented by an 8-bit value.

The model is intended to alter each color channel's LSBs. Each pixel comprises 24 bits, although only the LSB of each channel is modified for data encoding, resulting in minimal alteration to the image that remains visually undetectable.

Upon loading the image, the confidential data requiring encoding is transformed into a binary string. This transformation is essential because the binary representation facilitates the efficient manipulation of individual bits inside the image pixels. To facilitate the straightforward decoding of the encoded message, a specific sequence of characters is affixed to the binary data. This sequence functions as a delimiter or marker, signifying the conclusion of the secret data during the decoding process. This marker is essential for differentiating between the embedded data and any extraneous noise or information present in the image.

The subsequent step is to initiate the encoding process. The model processes each pixel in the image sequentially. The red, green, and blue color components are extracted for each pixel. Each component is transformed into its binary representation, and the LSB of each component is altered to correlate with the respective bit from the binary representation of the secret data. The model sequentially analyzes each color component R, G, and B, substituting the least significant bit of each with the subsequent bit of the secret data until all data is encoded. After the secret data encoding is completed, the image is revised, and the altered image is preserved as a new file. The encoded image closely resembles the original, as the alterations to the pixel values are negligible and undetectable to the human eye. The flow chart for encoding cover images with secret text data without DWT is shown in Figure 1. The patient's brain image is the cover image into which the patient's text details are embedded, resulting in a stegoimage equivalent to the cover image of the patient's brain image.

Fig 1. LSB Embedding Model

3.1.2 EXTRACTION MODEL

After the encoding phase, the model incorporates a decoding mechanism. The user inputs the encoded stegoimage to extract the concealed text data. The model analyzes the image and processes each pixel in the same manner as during the encoding phase. It retrieves the LSBs from every pixel of red, green, and blue components. The extracted segments are concatenated to create a binary string that signifies the concealed data. The binary string is subsequently divided into 8-bit segments, each denoting a byte of the original confidential information. The model subsequently transforms these binary segments into characters, recovering the original text's hidden data. The decoding process persists until the particular sequence is identified, signifying the conclusion of the confidential data. Upon identifying the stopping sequence, the model ceases picture analysis and returns the decoded data.

This guarantees that only the desired data is recovered from the image, while any residual noise or superfluous data is disregarded. By restricting alterations to the LSBs of image, the model guarantees that the encoded data does not significantly affect the image's visual quality. The concealed data can solely be identified by extracting the LSBs from the pixel values, which are generally impervious to conventional image alterations like compression or scaling.

Figure 2 shows the flow chart for extracting the patient's text details from the stegoimage. The stegoimage of the patient's brain image combines the cover image and the patient's text details. The patient's text details are extracted from the stego brain image.

Fig 2. LSB Extracting Model

The model emphasizes the LSB approach for steganography, utilizing its simplicity and efficacy in data embedding within images. The method is uncomplicated, as it solely entails fundamental image processing operations and operates directly on the image's pixel values. The primary benefits of this method include its straightforward implementation, negligible effect on the image's visual aesthetics, and comparatively low computing expense. This technique has disadvantages, including vulnerability to specific image-processing attacks that can compromise the integrity of the encoded data. Notwithstanding these constraints, the model offers a user-friendly and effective method for concealing secret data within images, rendering it a compelling option for fundamental steganography applications.

3.2 PROPOSED MODEL WITH DWT

The DWT is a powerful mathematical tool for analyzing and processing signals and images [12,13]. Unlike traditional transforms, such as the Fourier transform, which only offers frequency information, the DWT provides both frequency and spatial (or time) information, making it ideal for multi-resolution analysis applications. This property of DWT allows it to capture different levels of detail within a signal or image at various scales, making it particularly effective for tasks such as image compression, denoising, and feature extraction. At its core, the DWT transforms an image or signal into a set of coefficients representing various frequency components. These components are typically categorized into approximation coefficients representing the low-frequency components and detail coefficients representing high-frequency components. The DWT decomposes an image into multiple frequency bands, usually referred to as low-low (LL), low-high (LH), high-low (HL), and high-high (HH). Each of these bands captures different levels of detail, with the LL band representing the approximation of the image and the other bands representing various levels of detail in the horizontal, vertical, and diagonal directions. The DWT can be applied recursively to capture further levels of detail in an image, providing a multi-resolution representation.

One of the key advantages of the DWT is its ability to perform multi-resolution analysis. This enables the model to analyze the image at different scales, which is particularly useful in applications where image details at multiple resolutions must be preserved. The DWT also allows for effective compression of images, as less important details (captured in the high-frequency bands) can be discarded, leading to reduced data sizes while retaining most of the significant image information. In addition to compression, the DWT is widely used for image denoising. By thresholding the wavelet coefficients in the high-frequency bands, noise can be effectively removed while preserving the important features of the image. This ability to separate important features from noise makes DWT an excellent tool for cleaning images without losing essential details.

The DWT is also utilized in steganography, where it is used to hide data within the image without significantly affecting its visual quality. The high-frequency components of the image, which contain details that are less perceptible to the human eye, are often modified to embed the hidden data. This technique is more robust to common image manipulations, such as compression or noise addition than traditional pixel-based methods. While the DWT offers numerous advantages, it does have some drawbacks. One challenge is the computational complexity of the transform, particularly when applied to large datasets. While efficient algorithms exist for performing the DWT, they still require more computational resources compared to simpler transforms, such as the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT). Depending on the chosen wavelet, the DWT may introduce block-like artifacts, especially in image compression applications when the bitrates are low. These artifacts can degrade the image's visual quality, although this can be mitigated with careful selection of wavelet functions.

In conclusion, the DWT is a versatile and powerful tool that provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing signals and images. It enables efficient multi-resolution analysis, making it ideal for image compression, denoising, and feature extraction tasks. In steganography, the DWT offers improved robustness against image manipulation and allows for high-fidelity data embedding, which is crucial for applications requiring both high-quality images and secure data hiding. The trade-offs in computational complexity and potential artifacts should be considered when applying DWT in practical applications, but overall, it remains a highly effective tool in digital signal processing.

3.2.1 EMBEDDING MODEL WITH DWT

The suggested model combines LSB steganography with DWT to create a hybrid method that improves the security and robustness of data concealment. The concept employs the simplicity of LSB steganography to embed confidential data into the LSB of a picture while integrating the DWT for preprocessing the secret data. The DWT transformation enhances complexity and security by altering data in the frequency domain, rendering the encoded data less susceptible to common image-processing alterations such as compression, cropping, or resizing. Integrating these two techniques improves the stealth of the encoded message and offers resilience against typical visual distortions.

This model employs a 1D-DWT to divide the secret data into low-frequency and high-frequency components. The low-frequency components generally contain most of the signal's energy and exhibit greater resilience to picture alterations, rendering them optimal for embedding purposes. Consequently, post-transformation, only the low-frequency coefficients are preserved. These coefficients encapsulate the fundamental information of the original data and are less susceptible to modification during standard image-processing procedures. The DWT technique, particularly the *Haar wavelet*, is employed here for its simplicity and effectiveness in converting data into a more compact representation.

The coefficients derived from the DWT are subsequently converted into a binary data string suitable for embedding within the image. The transformation of DWT coefficients into binary format guarantees that the confidential data is encoded appropriately for concealment inside the LSB of image pixels.

Upon preprocessing the data with DWT, it is subsequently prepared for encoding into the image. The image undergoes a transformation in which its pixels are altered to encode confidential information. The LSB of the image's red, green, and blue color channels are substituted with the bits of the confidential data. The LSB approach operates by embedding data into the LSB of pixel values, which are least noticeable to the human eye, hence preserving the image's visual quality with minimal impact. The confidential information is integrated into these bits by systematically substituting each least significant bit of the pixel values with the corresponding bits of the confidential message. The encoding procedure persists until all confidential data has been integrated into the cover image.

A specific delimiter is appended to the end of the secret data before encoding to prevent misinterpretation of the hidden message's conclusion during the decoding process. This delimiter, a sequence of characters, functions as a marker to signify the conclusion of the encoded data. This phase guarantees that the decoding algorithm can precisely determine when to cease data extraction from the image, preventing extraneous data from being included in the decoded message. Upon completion of the encoding process, the image, now embedded with the concealed secret data, is preserved as the output stegoimage. To the human eye, the encoded image closely resembles the original brain image, preserving a significant degree of imperceptibility, which is the primary benefit of employing LSB steganography. The flow chart for encoding cover images with secret text data with DWT is shown in Figure 3. The patient's brain image is the cover image into which the patient's text details are embedded using the DWT technique, resulting in a stegoimage, which is equivalent to the cover image of the patient's brain image.

Fig 3. Flow Chart of embedding module with DWT

3.2.2 EXTRACTION MODEL USING DWT

The decoding procedure commences by obtaining the LSB from each pixel of the encoded image. The LSB from each pixel's red, green, and blue color channels are aggregated and concatenated into a binary string. The binary string is subsequently processed to revert it to the original secret message. The binary data is divided into 8-bit segments and subsequently transformed into characters representing the original message. The procedure persists until the delimiter is encountered, indicating the conclusion of the encoded message. Upon complete extraction of the encoded message, the final phase of the decoding procedure is inverting the preceding DWT transformation. The DWT utilized in encoding was employed to preprocess the confidential data, and it is now inverted to restore the original confidential data. The coefficients included in the image are reverted to their corresponding frequency components, and the IDWT is utilized to recover the original data. The DWT reversal guarantees that the decoded data closely resembles the original secret message, enabling the user to retrieve the concealed information.

The suggested model integrates the spatial domain of LSB with the frequency domain of DWT, offering a more resilient and secure approach for data concealment in images. The application of DWT minimizes data vulnerability to manipulation, as low-frequency components are less prone to alteration during standard image-processing operations. This hybrid method significantly enhances classic LSB steganography, offering superior security and improved resilience against common image distortions. Moreover, the model preserves the simplicity of LSB while leveraging the enhanced security provided by DWT, rendering it an efficient approach for secure data embedding. Figure 4 shows the flow chart for extracting the patient's text details from the stegoimage using IDWT. The stegoimage of the patient's brain image combines the cover image and the patient's text details. The patient's text details are extracted from the stego brain image with the help of IDWT.

Fig 4. Flow chart for decoding and extracting the secret data using IDWT

4. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

This model does utilize frequency domain changes, such as the DWT, which are occasionally included in more sophisticated steganography approaches. The model functions exclusively in the spatial domain, concentrating solely on altering the LSB of the image pixels.

The DWT techniques provide benefits like enhanced resilience against image processing attacks such as compression, this model is intended to be straightforward and efficient for scenarios where the main objectives are to illustrate fundamental steganography concepts, facilitate data embedding, and guarantee imperceptibility.

4.1. DEFINITIONS

4.1.1 THE MEAN SQUARED ERROR (MSE)

It is the Error between the original image and the stegoimage [14] using Equation 1:

$$MSE = \frac{\sum(y_i - p_i)^2}{n} \text{-----(1)}$$

where y_i is the observed pixel values

p_i is the corresponding modified pixel values of y_i

i is the number of pixels that varies from 1 to n

n is the total number of pixels in an image.

The Σ indicates that a summation is performed over all values of i .

4.1.2 THE PEAK SIGNAL-TO-NOISE RATIO (PSNR)

It is a metric that quantifies the imperceptibility of embedded data, specifically assessing the extent to which the stego-image preserves the quality of the original image post-data embedding [15]. Elevated PSNR values signify that the stego-image exhibits superior quality and less distortion, as shown in Equation 2:

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{MAX^2}{MSE} \right) \text{-----(2)}$$

Where:

MAX: The maximum possible pixel value in the image (e.g., 255 for an 8-bit image).

MSE: The Mean Squared Error between the original image and the stego-image.

4.1.3 CAPACITY:

It refers to the volume of data that may be altered within a cover image without compromising its integrity [16]. The steganographic embedding process must maintain the statistical characteristics of the cover image alongside its perceptual quality, as given in Equation 3:

$$\text{Hiding Capacity} = \frac{\text{The number of bits embedded in the cover image}}{\text{the number of pixels in the cover image}} \text{-----(3)}$$

4.2. RESULT ANALYSIS

To address these constraints, academics have suggested hybrid approaches that integrate the advantages of both LSB and DWT. Integrating these two strategies enables the attainment of equilibrium among data capacity, resilience, and imperceptibility. In hybrid LSB-DWT methodologies, the picture is initially processed by DWT to partition it into several frequency sub-bands. The confidential data is subsequently integrated into the high-frequency sub-bands utilizing DWT, while LSB is utilized for data embedding in the spatial domain (the pixel values). This dual embedding technique improves the performance of the steganography process by providing greater embedding capacity than DWT alone, while also ensuring the secret data is resistant to typical image modifications.

4.2.1 PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF MODEL USING LSB:

Over time, numerous advancements to LSB have been suggested to augment its resilience and security. The adaptive LSB approach is an enhancement that modifies the number of bits utilized for embedding based on the pixel's value, to render the alterations less detectable. Notwithstanding these improvements, LSB continues to be susceptible to basic modifications and image alterations that may jeopardize the concealed data. The specific patient's brain image is used as the cover image, as shown in Figure 5 (a). The research aims to embed the text details of patients into the cover image of the patient to generate stegoimage as shown in Figure 5 (b), which is the same as the patient's cover image.

(a) Brain image of the patient [16] before encoding (b) Stegoimage

Fig 5. The patient's cover and stegoimages using the LSB technique

The text details include the patient's name, family history, occupation, history, gender, and other details in Table 1 embedded into the cover image to obtain stegoimage with LSB technique.

Table 1: Patient details used for the LSB technique embedding

Patient Details

Name: John Doe

Age: 32 years

Gender: Male

Occupation: Software Engineer

Presenting Complaint: Persistent headache and occasional seizures for 3 months.

>Clinical History

Duration of Symptoms: 3 months

>Associated Symptoms:

Mild dizziness.

Blurred vision during headaches.

No history of trauma or infection.

Past Medical History:

No significant medical conditions.

No known allergies.

>Family History:

No family history of neurological disorders or malignancies.

Lifestyle Factors:

Non-smoker, occasional alcohol consumption.
Sedentary lifestyle due to desk job.
>Physical Examination
General Examination: Normal.
Neurological Examination:
Motor and sensory functions are intact.
Reflexes normal.
Cranial nerves: No abnormalities detected.

The text details include the patient's name, family history, occupation, history, gender, and other details extracted from the LSB technique given in Table 2, which is the same as the original details of the patient.

Table 2: Retrieved Patient's details with LSB Technique

Patient Details
Name: John Doe
Age: 32 years
Gender: Male
Occupation: Software Engineer
Presenting Complaint: Persistent headache and occasional seizures for 3 months.
>Clinical History
Duration of Symptoms: 3 months
>Associated Symptoms:
Mild dizziness.
Blurred vision during headaches.
No history of trauma or infection.
Past Medical History:
No significant medical conditions.
No known allergies.
>Family History:
No family history of neurological disorders or malignancies.
Lifestyle Factors:
Non-smoker, occasional alcohol consumption.
Sedentary lifestyle due to desk job.
>Physical Examination
General Examination: Normal.
Neurological Examination:
Motor and sensory functions are intact.
Reflexes normal.
Cranial nerves: No abnormalities detected.

The results of our performance analysis are presented in Table 3, which illustrates the relationship between embedding capacity and PSNR for the steganographic model with LSB technique. The data indicates a low embedding capacity correlates with a comparatively high PSNR. At a capacity of 0.435 bpp, the PSNR measures 77.08 dB. This signifies negligible distortion in the image, guaranteeing superior visual quality. With an increase in embedding capacity to 0.54 bpp, the PSNR decreases to 71.79 dB. This trend persists with additional capacity increments. At a capacity of 1.53 bpp, the PSNR measures 70.73 dB, whereas at 1.78 bpp, it measures 67.38 dB.

The data indicate that moderate enhancements in capacity lead to a progressive decline in image quality, while the photos remain acceptable. Nevertheless, when the embedding capacity is substantially augmented, the PSNR declines more markedly. At a capacity of 8.21 bpp, the PSNR measures 61.49 dB; however, at 10.2 bpp, the PSNR declines to 57.08 dB. These numbers signify a more significant deterioration in visual quality, with increased distortion apparent.

Table 3. Variations of capacity and PSNR with the LSB technique

Sl No.	Capacity (bpp)	PSNR (db)
1	0.435	77.08
2	0.54	71.79
3	1.53	70.73
4	1.78	67.38
5	8.21	61.49
6	10.2	57.08

The investigation reveals an inverse correlation between embedding capacity and PSNR. Increased embedding capacity results in diminished PSNR values, signifying a decline in image quality. This trade-off is characteristic of steganographic methods, wherein augmenting the quantity of concealed data typically compromises the visual integrity of the cover image. The findings highlight the necessity of equilibrating capacity and picture quality in the design of steganographic systems, especially for applications demanding high-fidelity image retention. The variations of PSNR with capacity using the LSB technique are shown in the graph in Figure 6. It is noticed that the PSNR decreases with an increase in capacity.

Fig 6. Correlation of PSNR and CAPACITY with LSB

4.2.2 PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF MODEL USING DWT

The constraints of LSB-based steganography have led academics to investigate frequency-domain methods for data embedding, with DWT emerging as a significant tool. The DWT is a mathematical method that converts images from the spatial domain to the frequency domain by breaking them into multiple frequency components. The image is segmented into many sub-bands according to its low and high-frequency components.

This segregation facilitates the incorporation of data into the high-frequency sub-bands, less impacted by compression and other image alterations. DWT-based steganography provides numerous benefits compared to LSB, such as enhanced resilience to typical image alterations, including JPEG compression and noise introduction. The information within the wavelet coefficients is more stable and less susceptible to detection by rudimentary image processing techniques. Furthermore, DWT facilitates the dispersion of concealed information, hence complicating the detection of secret data by attackers employing statistical techniques.

The steganography techniques, particularly those integrating LSB with DWT, offer a viable approach for safe, high-capacity, and resilient data concealment approaches. The advancements in this domain demonstrate an ongoing endeavor to surmount the constraints of singular methodologies and deliver more efficient and safe solutions for contemporary steganography applications. The specific patient's brain image is used as the cover image, as shown in Figure 7 (a). The research aims to embed the text details of patients into the cover image of the patient to generate stegoimage, as shown in Figure 7 (b), which is the same as the patient's cover image.

(a) Brain image of the patient before encoding

(b) Stegoimage

Fig 7. The patient's cover and stegoimages using DWT

The text details include the patient's name, family history, occupation, history, gender, and other details in Table 4 embedded into the cover image to obtain a stegoimage with the LSB technique.

Table 4: Patient details used for the DWT technique embedding

<p>Patient Details Name: John Doe Age: 32 years Gender: Male Occupation: Software Engineer Presenting Complaint: Persistent headache and occasional seizures for 3 months. >Clinical History Duration of Symptoms: 3 months >Associated Symptoms: Mild dizziness. Blurred vision during headaches. No history of trauma or infection. Past Medical History: No significant medical conditions. No known allergies. >Family History: No family history of neurological disorders or malignancies. Lifestyle Factors: Non-smoker, occasional alcohol consumption. Sedentary lifestyle due to desk job. >Physical Examination General Examination: Normal. Neurological Examination: Motor and sensory functions are intact. Reflexes normal. Cranial nerves: No abnormalities detected.</p>

The text details include the patient's name, family history, occupation, history, gender, and other details extracted from the IDWT technique given in Table 5, which is the same as the original details of the patient.

Table 5: Retrieved Patient's details using IDWT

<p>Patient Details Name: John Doe Age: 32 years Gender: Male Occupation: Software Engineer Presenting Complaint: Persistent headache and occasional seizures for 3 months. >Clinical History Duration of Symptoms: 3 months >Associated Symptoms: Mild dizziness. Blurred vision during headaches. No history of trauma or infection. Past Medical History: No significant medical conditions. No known allergies. >Family History:</p>
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No family history of neurological disorders or malignancies.

Lifestyle Factors:

Non-smoker, occasional alcohol consumption.

Sedentary lifestyle due to desk job.

>Physical Examination

General Examination: Normal.

Neurological Examination:

Motor and sensory functions are intact.

Reflexes normal.

Cranial nerves: No abnormalities detected.

The results of our performance analysis are presented in Table 6, which illustrates the relationship between embedding capacity and PSNR for the steganographic model with DWT.

Table 6. Variations of capacity and PSNR with the DWT technique

Sl NO.	Capacity (bpp)	PSNR (db)
1	0.435	83.08
2	0.54	70.53
3	1.53	67.12
4	1.78	63.47
5	8.21	56.38
6	10.2	52.75

The data indicates poor embedding capacity correlates with an exceptionally high PSNR. At a capacity of 0.435 bpp, the PSNR measures 83.08 dB, signifying exceptional visual quality with negligible distortion in the image. This indicates that the DWT-based steganographic model is exceptionally proficient in preserving image quality at minimal embedding capacities. With an increase in embedding capacity to 0.54 bpp, the PSNR decreases to 70.53 dB. This reduction is substantial while yet preserving a relatively high standard of image quality. Subsequent augmentations in capacity to 1.53 bpp and 1.78 bpp yield PSNR values of 67.12 dB and 63.47 dB, respectively. The results demonstrate that the model can support moderate volumes of embedded data while maintaining satisfactory image quality. Nevertheless, a significant augmentation in embedding capacity results in a more pronounced decline in PSNR values. At a capacity of 8.21 bpp, the PSNR measures 56.38 dB, whereas at 10.2 bpp, it declines to 52.75 dB. These values indicate a significant deterioration in visual quality, with increased distortion levels evident. The investigation reveals an inverse correlation between embedding capacity and PSNR in the DWT-based steganographic model. Increased embedding capacity results in diminished PSNR values, signifying a decline in image quality. This trade-off underscores the necessity of reconciling capacity and image quality in steganographic systems. The implementation of DWT in the steganographic model seems to enhance image quality at reduced capacities relative to models lacking DWT, rendering it appropriate for applications that emphasize high-fidelity image preservation while integrating concealed data.

The variations of PSNR with capacity using the DWT technique are shown in the graph in Figure 8. It is noticed that the PSNR decreases with an increase in capacity.

Fig 8. Correlation of PSNR and CAPACITY when DWT is used

5. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the integration of Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) with the Least Significant Bit (LSB) technique for steganography markedly enhances both the capacity for concealed data and the quality of the image. The conventional LSB technique is frequently employed due to its simplicity and efficiency; yet, it is typically constrained by drawbacks, including diminished image quality and decreased robustness when substantial data is embedded. The introduction of DWT allows us to utilize the image's frequency domain, where embedding data in the low-frequency components minimizes the perceptibility of alterations to the human eye. This results in a significant enhancement of the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and a decrease in the Mean Squared Error (MSE), signifying improved image quality preservation.

The primary benefit of employing DWT alongside LSB is its capacity to disseminate secret data across both spatial and frequency domains, enhancing resistance to attacks like compression or noise addition that usually impair the efficacy of solely spatial domain methods. DWT-based approaches exhibit greater resilience to image processing procedures, rendering them suitable for practical applications where pictures may experience transformations or alterations.

The DWT-enhanced LSB approach possesses a much greater capacity for data embedding, allowing for the concealment of larger volumes of information inside the image while maintaining visual quality without discernible degradation. The enhancement, along with the augmented security offered by the frequency domain approach, establishes the DWT-based LSB method as an optimal selection for contemporary steganography applications, especially in domains necessitating high capacity and strong security, such as medical imaging and digital forensics.

The study's findings underscore the efficacy of DWT in enhancing the performance of steganography systems. The expanded capacity, security, and quality retention of the DWT-augmented LSB technique render it an attractive option for future research and practical applications in secure communication and data protection.

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